

THERMAL STRESSES IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Summary

The influence of thermal stresses on the mechanical properties of metal matrix composites is considered. A method is derived for calculating the internal stresses appearing in fibrous composites due to differences in thermal expansion coefficients. Special attention is paid to plastic and creep conditions in the matrix phase. Two methods to consider such properties have been employed. The theory is confirmed by dilatometer tests of tungsten fiber reinforced stainless steel. The analysis shows that considerable internal stresses appear in composites when subjected to heating and cooling.

Introduction

There is currently, considerable interest in composite materials. Metal matrices and refractory fiber reinforcements are being studied as potential materials in gas-turbine components, such as rotor blades. The main advantages when composites are introduced in an aero-engine is the possibility of increased material temperature and higher strength to weight ratios as compared with superalloys.

Among the systems studied, superalloys reinforced with tungsten fibers have been the subject of extensive research [1-3].

Thermal fatigue and thermal stresses are a great obstacle to the use of high temperature composites [4]. Many combinations of material, considered for use in reinforced metal - matrix composites, have appreciable differences in thermal expansion coefficients. When the composites are used as turbine blade materials, their temperature is cycled between say 30 and 1100°C very rapidly. Typical superalloy⁻⁶ matrices have coefficients of thermal expansion from about 16×10^{-6} to 19×10^{-6} [m/m °C] over this temperature range. Fibers often have lower coefficients than the matrices. For tungsten the coefficient is about 5×10^{-6} and for graphite it is -0.2 to 1.1×10^{-6} [m/m °C] over the same temperature range. In a system of, for instance, tungsten fibers in a superalloy matrix the difference in coefficients is great enough to give matrix stresses above the yield stress. At a temperature above say 900°C creep must also be taken into account.

There are a number of analyses of the internal stresses, due to differences in thermal expansion [5-8]. Most consider situations in which both phases are elastic. The analyses of de Silva and Chadwick [9] incorporates plasticity effects and Garmong [10] has included creep deformation as well. A thick-walled cylinder is used as composite model in some analyses [11-13].

Theory

In this analysis we consider a matrix material containing parallel, continuous fibers. We make the assumptions that perfect bonds exist between the fibers and the matrix and that deformations remain essentially one dimensional. Furthermore the stresses and strains are taken to be uniform within each phase and the composite is assumed to be metallurgically stable.

If the axial stresses in the fibers and the matrix are assumed to be in equilibrium we have the familiar rule of mixtures

$$\sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) = \sigma_t \quad (1)$$

where the subscripts f and m refer to fiber and matrix respectively. σ_t is the stress applied externally to the composite. V_f is volume fraction of fibers.

In order to ensure continuity at the fiber - matrix interface at a small temperature change δT , we must have

$$\frac{\delta \epsilon_m}{\delta T} + \alpha_m = \frac{\delta \epsilon_f}{\delta T} + \alpha_f \quad (2)$$

where ϵ is the mechanical strain and α the coefficient of thermal expansion.

For many practical reinforcements, e.g. W- and C-fibers, the creep term can be neglected compared with the creep term in matrix material. The fibers very often are brittle and the plastic term can be omitted. In this analysis therefore the fibers are assumed to be in an elastic state while the matrix suffers elastic, plastic and creep deformation. Thus, the effect of the difference in thermal expansions on the composite system can be expressed as

$$(\alpha_f - \alpha_m)\delta T = \delta\epsilon_{me} + \delta\epsilon_{mp} + \delta\epsilon_{mc} - \delta\epsilon_{fe} \quad (3)$$

where the subscripts e, p and c refer to elastic, plastic and creep deformations.

The elastic strain in the matrix is

$$\epsilon_{me} = \frac{\sigma_m}{E_m} \quad (4)$$

where E is the Young's modulus. The fiber strain can by the rule of mixture, eq (1), be given as

$$\epsilon_{fe} = \frac{\sigma_a - \sigma_m (1 - V_f)}{V_f E_f} \quad (5)$$

Due to changes both in temperature and stresses during a thermal cycle the plasticity and creep-terms in eq (3) are complicated. Two solutions, A and B, are derived here.

Version A

The stress-strain relation by Ludwik [14] is employed and the plastic term can be expressed as

$$\epsilon_{mp} = \left[\frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_{my}}{P} \right]^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (6)$$

where p and n are material constants and σ_{my} is the yield stress.

The matrix creep rate, $\dot{\epsilon}$, is mainly dependent on stress and temperature. When thermal stresses in composites are considered both stress and temperature vary during a cycle. Ashby [15] has shown by use of deformation maps, in which regions of stress and temperature different creep mechanisms are dominant. From such considerations the conclusion can be drawn that dislocation creep is predominant in our case. To describe the creep rate of the matrix material we employ the constitutive relation by Dorn [16]

$$\dot{\epsilon}_m = A \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{G} \right)^m \frac{Gb}{kT} D_0 e^{-Q/RT} \quad (7)$$

where A and m are empirical constants, G the matrix shear modulus,

b the Burgers vector, k Boltzmann's constant, R the gas constant, and D_0 and Q the pre-exponential constant and the activation constant for self-diffusion. This relation is well documented from the experimental point of view and data exist for the constants A and m for a wide variety of materials.

Due to the complexity of eq (3) with the employed expressions for plasticity and creep, the solutions are most readily obtained by numerical methods. It is suitable to write the equations in an incremental form, where a small change in temperature ΔT gives a change in stress $\Delta \sigma$. The creep deformation in each temperature increment is calculated by numerical integration. The internal stresses and strains can then be calculated by a iterative method. More details of the calculation are given in ref [17].

Version B

Version A is relatively simple and is based on readily available material data. However, the temperature dependence of the yield stress makes it inexact at changing temperatures. Under such conditions a more adequate description of plastic and creep properties is desirable. In order to formulate such a theory a constitutive model by Miller [18] for creep and plasticity is introduced into our thermal stress eq (3). This model contains two types of hardening parameters. In the first type the strength of the material remains equal in all directions, regardless of the axis of straining, (isotropic hardening D). The second type is directional, (kinematic hardening R). Prestraining a material in tension may strengthen it in the tensile direction but may weaken it in compression.

The model employed simulates such phenomena as cyclic hardening/softening, Bauschinger effect, strain-rate effects and annealing.

The composite model is here written in a differential form:

$$\dot{\sigma}_m = \beta(\alpha_m - \alpha_f) \frac{dT}{dt} + \dot{\epsilon}_{mpc} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\beta = \frac{V_f E_f E_m}{(1 - V_f)E_m + V_f E_f} \quad (9)$$

$\dot{\epsilon}_{mpc}$ is the nonelastic matrix strain-rate.

The nonelastic deformations in the matrix are given by Miller in three differential equations. The first is a single hyperbolic sine strain-rate equation:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{mpc} = B\theta^1 \left\{ \sinh \left[\left(\frac{|\sigma_m - R|}{D} \right)^{1.5} \right] \right\}^s \quad (10)$$

where

$$\theta^1 = \exp \left\{ \left[-\frac{Q}{0.6 RT_m} \right] \cdot \left[\ln \left(\frac{0.6 T_m}{T} \right) + 1 \right] \right\} \quad \text{for } T \leq 0.6 T_m \quad (11)$$

$$\theta' = \exp(-Q/RT) \text{ for } T \geq 0.6 T_m \quad (12)$$

The hardening parameters are given by:

$$\dot{R} = H_1 \dot{\epsilon}_{mpc} - H_1 B \theta' \left[\sinh(A_1 |R|) \right]^s \quad (13)$$

and

$$\dot{D} = H_2 |\dot{\epsilon}_{mpc}| \left[C_2 + |R| - (A_2/A_1) D^3 \right] - H_2 C_2 B \theta' \left[\sinh(A_2 D^3) \right]^s \quad (14)$$

$A_1, A_2, B, C_2, H_1, H_2, s,$ and Q are material constants. T_m is the melting temperature.

The system of first order differential equations are solved by a Runge Kutta Merson method and the internal composite stresses can be calculated for a arbitrary time-temperature relation.

Theoretical results

Figure 1 shows a plot of matrix and fiber stresses versus temperature for a W-2% ThO₂ fiber reinforced stainless steel, calculated by version A. The data used are given in Table I. The composite, contain-

Figure 1. Thermal stresses in a SS/W-2%ThO₂ composite containing 25% fibers. Thermal cycle 1475K → 300K → 1200K.

ing 25% fibers, is assumed to be stress-free at an initial temperature of 1450 K and is cooled to room temperature at a rate of 20 K/min followed by heating to 1200 K at the same rate. Since σ_f is a function of V_f and σ_m the discussion will be focused on σ_m .

Table I. Mechanical and physical data for stainless steel and W-2% ThO₂. Basis for calculation by version A.

Parameter	Value	Unit	Parameter	Value	Unit
α_f	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1/K	A	$6.3836 \cdot 10^{17}$	-
α_m	$17 \cdot 10^{-6} + 6 \cdot 10^{-9} x t_c$	1/K	b	$2.49 \cdot 10^{-10}$	m
E_f	$4.0 \cdot 10^5 - 55 x t_c$	MPa	m	7.7865	-
E_m	$1.93 \cdot 10^5 - 73.7 x t_c$	MPa	k	$1.38 \cdot 10^{-23}$	-
G_m	$8.0 \cdot 10^4 - 35.0 x t_c$	MPa	R	1.987	cal/mol · k
σ_{ym}	$200 - 0.18 x t_c$	MPa	Q	85000	cal/mol
B	$69 \cdot 10^7$	-	Do	$19.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-
n	0.5	-	σ_t	0	MPa

$$t_c = T - 273 \text{ } [^{\circ}\text{C}]$$

Figure 2. Matrix stresses versus temperature in a SS/W-2%ThO₂ composite containing 25% fibers. Thermal cycle 1465K → 300K → 1175K.

During cooling the matrix stress increases continuously because the matrix contracts faster than does the reinforcement. In the region between A and B in Figure 1 most of the developing stress is relaxed by creep. Around B the temperature becomes too low for creep to occur and the stress increases more rapidly. The yield stress is temperature dependent and here a linear relation is assumed. At point C the stress reaches the yield stress and during cooling to room temperature the matrix deforms plastically.

When the heating begins from point D, the matrix is unloaded in the absence of plastic and creep deformations. The composite is stress-free at E. Further heating causes compressive loading in the matrix and tensile stress in the reinforcement. At F the matrix stress reaches the elastic limit and continued heating causes plastic deformation in the matrix. The combination of increasing temperature, decreasing yield stress and a strain hardening in the material is not well known and the matrix stress in the region F-G is rather uncertain. When the stress level is high and the temperature increases, creep relaxes the stresses rather rapidly in region G-H. Temperatures above H gives low stresses, the creep rate slows down and there remains only a small compressive stress at 1200 K.

The matrix stress versus temperature for a tungsten fiber reinforced stainless steel, calculated by version B, is plotted in Figure 2. The material data, mainly from ref 18, are summarised in Table II. In this case the temperature-time relation is given by:

$$T = T_g + (T_s - T_g) e^{-\epsilon t} \quad (15)$$

where

T_s is the initial temperature and T_g is the final temperature, while ϵ is a constant. The composite is manufactured at 1465 K and cooled down to room temperature with $\epsilon = 0.015$. It is then cycled between 300 K and 1175 K with the same ϵ . The effect of deformation hardening in the matrix is evident in Figure 2. It is reflected by an increase in stress at room temperature for each cycle.

Table II Mechanical and physical data for stainless steel from ref 18. Basis for calculation by version B.

Parameter	Value	Unit	Parameter	Value	Unit
A_1	0.108	MPa^{-1}	H_1	1930	MPa
A_2	$2.27 \cdot 10^{-7}$	MPa^{-1}	H_2	100	-
B	$1.0 \cdot 10^{15}$	Sec^{-1}	S	5.8	-
C_2	0.69	MPa	Q	91000	cal/mol
E_m	$1.93 \cdot 10^5 - 73.7 \cdot t_c$	MPa	T_m	1800	K

The influence of volume fraction on matrix and fiber stresses is shown in Figure 3 and 4 respectively. This applies to the same composite system as before and the material data given in Table I are used. Three different volume fractions are used in the calculation (version A); $V_f = 0.25$; 0.50 ; and 0.75 . The composite is assumed stress-free at 1275 K and cooled down to 300 K at a rate of 20 K/min followed by heating to 1025 K at the same rate.

The matrix is deformed plastically during most of the temperature drop from 1275 K to room temperature. Compared to the increase in yield stress with decreasing temperature the deformation hardening can be neglected and this is why the matrix stress is almost independent of V_f for this temperature change, Figure 3. When the heating begins the matrix is deformed elastically and the higher V_f the more rapid composite unloading.

Figure 3. Matrix stress in a SS/W-2%ThO₂ composite as a function of volume fraction.

The fibers are deformed elastically and V_f has a very important effect on the stresses. The lower the volume fraction fibers the higher is the load on each, Figure 4. The compressive fiber stress at room temperature for $V_f = 0.25$ is about ten times higher than for $V_f = 0.75$ and a similar effect can be seen on the max fiber tensile stress around 800 K when the composite is heated.

Figure 4. Fiber stress in a SS/W-2%ThO₂ composite as a function of volume fraction.

Heating and cooling rates have effect on the creep deformation in the matrix. The fiber and matrix stresses, calculated by version A, for three thermal cycles with different cooling and heating rates are shown in Figure 5. The effect is obvious in the high temperature region where creep is important. The slower the cooling and heating rates the greater is the creep deformations.

Figure 5. Effect of cooling and heating rate on internal stresses in a SS/W-2%ThO₂ composite.

Experimental Procedure

The validity of the theoretical results was checked by thermal expansion measurement in a dilatometer.

Composite specimens were produced by a hot isostatic pressing (HIP) method. The reinforcement wire was a thoriated tungsten containing 2 wt % ThO₂ with a diameter of 0.3 mm. The matrix was an 18/8 stainless steel, type 304. The reinforcement wires were arranged in one direction in the matrix material and then enclosed in an outer cladding tube. The billets were hot isostatically compacted in two steps; first at 1275 K, 170 MPa for 1 hour and then at 1455 K, 190 MPa for 3 hours.

The specimens had a length of 100 mm and consisted of a composite core with a diameter of approximately 3 mm and an outer cladding of approximately 10 mm diameters. Metallographic observation of the composite cross-section, showed that the specimen was fully dense and that the fiber distribution was uniform, see Figure 6. An intermetallic layer, 12 μ m thick, had formed between the wire and matrix, see Figure 7.

Specimens for the dilatometer-tests were machined by centerless grinding to a diameter of 3.3 mm, and were cut to a length of 60 mm.

Figure 6. Composite cross section after HIP

Figure 7. Interface between fiber and matrix

Specimens with fiber volume fractions of 13 and 27 % were prepared. To protect the fibers against oxidation a thin disc was electron-beam welded on to each end, Figure 8.

The thermal expansion behavior of the specimens was examined in a temperature range between room temperature and 900°C. Length changes in the fiber direction were measured using a quartz tube dilatometer in which the specimen was kept in air at atmospheric pressure. The rate of temperature change during the tests was between 1 and 20 K/min.

Experimental Results

The composite was manufactured (and was presumably stress-free) at 1455 K. After pressing it was slowly cooled down to room temperature and then machined as described above. It was then thermally cycled at a controlled rate of 5 K/min in the dilatometer. The axial thermal elongation vs temperature for two cycles 300 K → 1200 K → 300 K for a composite containing 13% fibers is shown in Figure 9. Small corrections in the measured elongation were made for the ends of the specimen and for the fact that the temperature within the specimen lagged somewhat behind that indicated by the thermocouple placed close to the specimen surface. It can be seen clearly from the figure that the expansion / contraction behavior of the composite was not reversible. It was shown in the theoretical analysis that the hysteresis is due to plastic deformations in the matrix material. As a comparison the thermal expansion curves for the separate composite constituents are drawn in the figure.

The internal composite thermal stresses can be calculated from the difference between the free-fiber expansion and the measured composite expansion. The elongation $(\Delta l / l)_c$ of a composite c during a change in temperature in the absence of external loading is

$$\left(\frac{\Delta l}{l}\right)_c = \int_T^{T+\Delta T} \alpha_f dT + \Delta \epsilon_f \quad (16)$$

where the first term is the fiber expansion and the second term is a mechanical fiber strain increment due to internal stresses. An identical expression is valid for the matrix material, but in that case the mechanical strain includes, besides elastic, both plastic and creep terms and is more difficult to handle. Eq 16 gives the fiber stress

$$\sigma_f = \sigma_{f0} + \frac{1}{E_f} \left[\left(\frac{\Delta l}{l}\right)_c - \int_T^{T+\Delta T} \alpha_f \cdot dT \right] \quad (17)$$

where σ_{f0} is the initial stress of the fiber. The expansion coefficient α_f and Young's modulus E_f for the fiber are well-known and the fiber stress can be calculated with good accuracy.

To be able to transform the measured composite elongation to fiber stress it remains to determine the initial stress σ_{f0} . The composite in question was produced, and was stress-free, at 1455 K. When cooled down to room temperature the matrix has tensile and the reinforcement has compressive stresses.

The theoretical calculation made using the version A equations was based on the mechanical and physical property data summarized in Table I. The data were either taken from the literature or obtained by our own mechanical testing of the stainless steel and W-2 % ThO₂ fibers,

Figure 8. Composite specimen for dilatometer test

Figure 9. Axial thermal elongation vs temperature for a SS/W-2%ThO₂ composite containing 13% fibers

Figure 10. Thermal stresses in composite. Comparison between theory and dilatometer tests.

Figure 11. Cracks in the interface close to the end of a composite subjected to a dilatometer test.

heat treated under conditions similar to the composite production conditions. The fiber content, V_f , is an important parameter and was determined from micrographs after the tests.

For the calculation it was assumed that no stresses or strains exist in either phase at the initial production temperature of 1455 K and that the composite was cooled from this temperature at 20 K/min to 300 K. Thereafter the dilatometer-cycle conditions described above were used.

Figure 10 demonstrates that the shape of the calculated fiber stress vs temperature cycles are in satisfactory agreement with the experimental results. If the calculated value of the stress at 300 K, σ_{fo} , is correct then the calculated and experimental results agree to within ± 50 MPa throughout the entire dilatometer test. As expected the discrepancy is greatest in the regions of combined creep and plastic deformations.

The fiber stresses calculated by version B for the dilatometer test is also shown in Figure 10. The matrix properties is based on the data from stainless steel given in ref 18. The discrepancy in the region where the matrix is deformed non-elastic can to some extent depend on difficulties to feed in adequate material parameters in the calculation.

The micrographic analysis of the specimens after dilatometer tests show no cracks in fibers or matrix. Very close to the ends of the specimens cracks in the intermediate layer are observed, see Figure 11. Haener [19] has shown that the shear stress between fiber and matrix is high near the ends.

At room temperature the compressive fiber stress is approximately -1520 MPa in the composite considered. The matrix has, at the same temperature, a tensile stress of 225 MPa. The high compressive stress in the fibers at room temperature can be expected to make a corresponding contribution to the UTS of the composite. But at temperatures around 900 K a tensile stress develops in the reinforcement and a corresponding decrease in the composite strength is to be predicted.

Conclusions

The analysis presented above has shown that thermal stresses, arising from differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion of the constituents, are of such magnitudes that fiber damage and matrix fatigue is possible when the composite is subjected to heating-cooling cycles. The volume fraction of reinforcement is of great importance for the stresses especially in the fibers. Also the plastic properties and the yield stress of the matrix have a considerable influence on the thermal stresses. The creep deformation of the matrix has the effect of reducing the stresses at high temperatures. It is evident that the cooling and heating rate not is an important parameter.

Two versions, A and B, of the analysis of thermal stresses are used. Version A is based on equations, where the material parameters are well documented while version B is more complicated and the required material data is difficult to find. The fiber stresses calculated by version A for a few dilatometer cycles are in a good agreement with experimental results. If adequate material data exists version B should give a more satisfactory estimation of internal stresses for a composite subjected to a number of cycles.

For a composite, especially with a low fiber content, the fiber stresses at room temperature are considerable and must be taken into account when estimating the R.T. properties of the composite. At higher temperature the fiber stress becomes tensile and can be expected to cause a decrease of the composite yield strength.

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